

Review Article

A Comprehensive Review of the Ethnopharmacology, Phytochemistry, Pharmacology & Current Formulations of *Thymus vulgaris* Linn

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ABSTRACT

Thymus vulgaris Linn. (*T. vulgaris* Linn.) is a perennial wild shrub from Lamiaceae family native to the European, Mediterranean region and considered as a medicinal herb. Around 100 thyme species are accessible and considered as medicinal plant due to their phytonutrients, minerals, crude fibers and vitamins. From centuries people are considering it as an edible herb and widely used for medicinal purposes, culinary dishes and cosmetic industries because of its significant aromatic traits. *T. vulgaris* Linn. Majorly composed with thymol and carvacrol, flavonoids, antioxidants, etc. It is assigned of multi pharmacological activities such as anti-cancer, anti-microbial, anti-septic, anti-viral, anti-fungal, anti-nociceptive, immunomodulatory, against SARS Cov-2, expectorant, inhibit uterine contraction, anti-aging, appetite stimulant, induction of myeloma (Autophagic, apoptosis & ferroptosis), anti-Alzheimer, anti-osteoporosis, sedative, anti-helminthic, anti-amnesia, anti-depressant, anti-hypertension. This study, gathered almost 60% of research evidence of *T. vulgaris* Linn. In this review paper, aiming to comprehend the ethno botanical distribution of *T. Vulgaris* Linn along with nutritional values, major phytochemicals, pharmacological activities, formulations available and the existing gaps of the *T. Vulgaris* for further research.

INTRODUCTION

Thymus vulgaris Linn. is a medicinal herb as well as culinary herb mostly seen southern European region [1]. *T. vulgaris* L. or thyme also known as “garden Thyme”. The word ‘thyme’ derived from a Greek word which means ‘fumigate’ due to its

intense and balsamic odour (sweet smelling herb). It is an aromatic and perennial flowering plant being native in southern Europe but reports shows it distributes world-wide. It commercially used as a flavouring agent in food industries, due to its immense aromaticity [2]. Mint family belonged thyme plant was using since ancient civilization of

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Greek, Romans and Egyptians as natural preservation (Preserve body after death) due to its natural antiseptic and preservative quality. Romans were considered it as symbol of purification and valor (to clean living places, food flavour and liqueurs) [3].

Kingdom	Plantae
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Lamiales
Family	Lamiaceae
Subfamily	Nepetoideae
Genus	Thymus L.
Species	Thymus vulgaris L.

1.1. Plant description [4]:

Aerial stem part of *Thymus vulgaris* L.

Flowers of *Thymus vulgaris* L.

Seeds of *Thymus vulgaris* L.

Thymus vulgaris L. is a non woody persistent herb that grows in USDA (United States of Department of Agriculture) zones 5 to 9 (plant can survive winter -20 to -10 degrees Fahrenheit). Typically the plant grows around 0.5 to 1 foot in height and branch, which makes ideal for herb garden. It thrives in full sun, have the ability to survive in dry, rocky and polluted environment [6, 8]. Its pale purple flower bloom from May to July. Ornamental qualities gives culinary effect, often utilize to treat illness of respiratory and digestive system because of its antioxidant and antimicrobial properties [7].

1.2. Macroscopic morphology

Table 1: Microscopic characteristics of *Thymus vulgaris* L.

Plant part	Characteristics
Stem	Woody at base, herbaceous in upper parts and quadrangular (four-angled). <i>Blazevic et al. (2006)</i>
Leaves	Small, linear, ovate margins, green-gray coloured and haired gland dotted beneath. <i>S. Kokkini et al. (2003)</i>

Flower	Around 12 per whorl, tubular bilabiate calyx-4mm, didynamous stamens, purplish bilabiate corolla twice as long and style end in a bilobed stigma
Seed	Very small light weighted (length is about 0.9 mm & width 0.8mm), oval to spherical, smooth & dark brown to black color. <i>Ana Alimpic Aradski et al. (2023)</i>
Root	Woody, taproot, dense and fibrous. This structure helps the plant to adapt in rocky, dry and poor soils. <i>EthanBasch et al. (2004)</i>

1.3. Microscopic characteristics

Pharmacognostic characteristics

Leaf of *Thymus vulgaris* L. upper epidermis is covered with thick cuticle and have glandular (Major site for oil secretion) and glandular (unicellular) trichome. Mesophyll seen in dorsiventral with palisade cells beneath UE (Upper Epidermis) and lower spongy parenchyma. Amphi-stomatic & collateral vascular bundle- Xylem; facing to upper side & Phloem; Lower side [11, 12].

Morphology and microscopy of leaf (*Thymus vulgaris*)

Stem has single layered cuticle covered, unicellular non glandular and glandular capitate and peltate types trichome. Cortex seen beneath the epidermis made with collenchyma and parenchymatous cells with oil glands. Pericycle contains lignified fibres [13]. Large pith with parenchymatous cells and intercellular space. Well-developed phloem and radially arranged xylem with vessels, tracheids and fibers [14]. Flower of *Thymus vulgaris* L. is the main site for thymol and carvacrol. Bilabiate (4-5mm) tubular, 9 to 12 nerved calyx. Outer surface covered with capitate or peltate glandular trichomes and non-glandular hairs. Epidermal layer has pigment cells. Stamen/ Gynoecium is didynamous, small sized tricolpate pollen grains. Bicarpellary gynoecium has syncarpous ovary and four lobed deep style ending in bilobed stigma [13-15]. *Thymus vulgaris* L. has a smooth, small, oval to ovoid brownish seed. Seed coated with thick multi layered epidermis and thin layered endosperm rich in fixed oils. Small two cotyledons embryo and contain oil droplets which responsible for its aromatic and medicinal properties [14, 16].

2. Collection of data

Literature data (research and reviews) of *Thymus vulgaris* L. were gathered from electronic databases such as PubMed, WoS, Google Scholar, Springer Link, Science Direct and Wiley Blackwell. The peer reviewed journals and E books data were collected. Keyword related data included to know the taxonomy and gaps of research study conducted till now.

3. Ethnobotanical distribution:

Thymus vulgaris Linn. Perennial wild shrub from Lamiaceae family native to the European, Mediterranean region. Patil et al. (2021), Concluded that, *T. vulgaris* L. available in southern European only but now it is widely distributed globally [17, 18]. Apart from Europe it is grown in Australia, North Asia, North Africa, Canada and USA. In India, it is cultivated in the Western temperate Himalayas and Nilgiris [19].

4. Ethnobotanical Uses [20- 25]

Table 2; Ethnobotanical distribution of *Thymus vulgaris*

Region	Part	Preparation/ administration	Traditional use/ Pharmacological activity
India Himalayas Nilgiris Kashmir Himachal Pradesh	Leaves Essential Oil Whole Plant	Decoction	Culinary and medicinal use Flavouring agent in curries and soups Cough, cold, asthma, and sore throat & natural antiseptic
North Africa (Egypt)	Leaves Oil	Infusions Powder	Digestive ailments Traditional ritual Food preservation
Saharan region Morocco	Leaves Flowers	Infusion	Stomach ache, colic, respiratory disorders, carminative & antimicrobial

Algeria Tunisia	Aerial Part		
West Africa Nigeria Cameroon	Whole Aerial Part Leaves	Decoction poultice	Malaria, fever, cough, wounds and skin infections
South Africa	Leaves, Oil	Infusion	Respiratory ailments, skin infections and as disinfectant
Europe Spain France Italy Bulgaria	Leaves, Flowers Oil	Powder Infusion	Widely used in cooking (meats, soups, cheeses); medicinal use for sore throat, bronchitis, antiseptic mouthwash and digestive tonic.
Turkey	Leaves Flowers Seeds	Tea Poultices	Antimicrobial, antioxidant & digestive aid
Iran	Leaves Stems Oil	Infusion	Cough, asthma, pain relief, antiseptic and analgesic agent
Greece	Leaves, Flowers	Decoction	Colds, indigestion and as tonic
US & UK	Leaves, essential oil	Powder Oil	Disinfectant, cosmetics, mouth wash and tooth paste

5. Phytochemical constituents:

T. vulgaris L. shows aneuploidy [15] the different plant of same species possess different chromosomal number. It shows the evolutionary changes. Researches shows that these all plants shows various chemo types. Recent studies identified 6 different chemo types (like geraniol, sabinene hydride, linalool, thymol and carvacrol). It might be because of diverse essential oil composition [19].

Phytochemicals are called as bioactive compounds, which found in plants that play a

crucial role in treat and managing diseases [26]. Thymol is one the major phyto-constituents, present abundantly in *Thymus vulgaris* L. carvacrol, geraniol, α -terpineol, 4-thujanol, linalool, 1,8-cineole, myrcene, γ -terpinene, and p-cymene. These bioactive chemicals reported that, possess antitussive, antispasmodic, anticancer, antibroncholytic Etc [27]. Butylated hydroxytoluene, butylated hydroxyanisole, propyl gallate, (E)-cinnamaldehyde, menthol, L-menthol, cuminaldehyde, eucalyptol, eugenol, methyl chavicol, monoterpenes, p-cymene [28] also active constituents.

Table 3; pharmacological activities of *Thymus vulgaris* L.

Extract	Chemical constituent		Pharmacological activity
Aqueous Extract [28]	Phenolic compound	Thymol [29] (2-isopropyl-5-methylphenol)	Antitumor, antiseptic, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antioxidant & free radical scavenging
		Carvacrol [30]	Antifungal, antiviral, anticancer and anti-inflammatory activities
	Flavonoids	Luteolin 3',4',5,7-tetrahydroxyflavone [31]	Anticancer, anti-inflammatory activity & Hypertension

		Apigenin [32]	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antibacterial and antiviral.
		Quercetin [33]	wound healing, Antioxidant, - inflammatory, antimicrobial, anti- Alzheimer's.
		Naringenin [34]	Cancer, Diabetes, obesity, hyper-lipidemia
		Eriocitrin	Anti-angiogenic [35], Lung adenocarcinoma [36], hepatic steatosis [37] & Osteoarthritis [38]
	Phenolic acids	Rosmarinic acid	Cancer [39], Anti-angiogenic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, and antimicrobial properties [40].
		Ferulic acid [41]	Antidiabetic, Neuroprotective, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
		Chlorogenic acid [42, 43]	Neurodegenerative disorders, kidney injuries, & anti-tumor activities
Ethanollic extract	Leaf	Quinic acid	Dengue [44], atherosclerosis [45], retinoblastoma [46]
		Carvacrol	Anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-oxidant, diabetes mellitus, antibacterial & antimicrobial [46-48]
		Thymol	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal, antiseptic antitumor & antispasmodic
		Indole	Respiratory diseases, antiviral, steatosis, anticancer [49, 50]

6. Pharmacological evidences:

Ethno pharmacological reports indicate that *T. vulgaris* Linn. has been employed from centuries in the various treatments such as respiratory ailments, gastro intestinal disorders, preservatives etc. Nikolic. M et al (2014), reported that essential oils has thymol, carvacrol, p-cymene, linalool, α -pinene, β - pinene as major constituent with high antimicrobial, antioxidant effects, antispasmodic [52] (Ali, B. et al. 2015) & preservative uses [53]. Research investigations reported that *T. vulgaris* has anti-cancer, anti-microbial, etc [54, 2].

6.1. Anticancer:

N Adham A et al (2020), tested chloroform and ethyl acetate extract of *Thymus vulgaris* L. against blood cancer and multiple melanoma cells. It showed strong anticancer activity by arresting cell or apoptosis, Autophagic and ferroptosis [50]. [Kubatka P et al (2019)], Dried *Thymus vulgaris*

was tested in rats and mice with breast cancer and in human breast cancer cells. Showed strong chemo preventive and therapeutic effects against breast cancer [55]. Niksic H et al. (2021), was evaluated in-vitro anti-proliferative activity (MTT assay) on three cell lines from human (breast adenoma MCF-7, Lung carcinoma H460 & acute lymphoblastic leukaemia MOLT-4). The study concluded that essential oil of *Thymus vulgaris* L. has strong anticancer activity [56]. Kowalczyk A et al. (2020), reported that thymol inhibited the carcinoma cell lines (prostate, non-small-cell lung carcinoma & highly metastatic breast adenocarcinoma). It showed a selective anti proliferative effect on cancer [57]. 58.

Fatima K, Luqman S et al. (2022), reported that carvacrol (essential oil) inhibited enzymes involving in carcinogenesis; ornithine decarboxylase (ODC), cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), lipoxygenase-5 (LOX-5) and hyaluronidase (HYAL). It induced apoptosis in cancer cells.

Around 72% of tumor growth inhibited in mice (75 mg/kg) [58]. *Thymus vulgaris* methanolic extract slows the growth of breast cancer cells (MCF-7, MDA-MB-231) by blocking proliferation, migration and colony formation. It also triggers cell death through apoptosis and autophagy. These results suggest its potential in breast cancer treatment, but further animal studies are needed [59].

6.2. Anti-microbial:

Wirtu SF et al (2024), tested hexane, chloroform, and methanol extracts, along with isolated fractions of *Thymus vulgaris*, against different bacteria. The findings show its bioactive compounds have strong potential in controlling microbial infections [60]. Mohammadmehdi Fani et al. (2017), reported that *Thymus vulgaris* oil showed antimicrobial effects, forming inhibition zones of 7.5–42 mm. The lowest MICs were for *S. pyogenes* (1.9 mg/mL) and *S. mutans* (3.6 mg/mL), while *C. albicans* (16.3 mg/mL), *A. actinomycetemcomitans* (32 mg/mL), and *P. gingivalis* (32 mg/mL) required higher concentrations [61]. Studies have shown that *Thymus vulgaris* essential oil inhibits the growth of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus saprophyticus* isolated from meat products. It exhibited both inhibitory and killing effects (MIC: 64–512 µg/mL; MBC: 256–1,024 µg/mL), reduced bacterial adhesion, and enhanced the action of some antibiotics, suggesting its promise as a natural agent against foodborne pathogens [62].

6.3. Anti-inflammatory:

Mohammad Reza Khazdair et al (2021), reported that *T. vulgaris* and thymol reduced IL-6, IL-1β and tumor necrosis factor α (TNFα) at both gene and proteins levels [63]. The study found that TEO (Thyme Essential Oil) and thymol increased

antioxidant enzyme activity (CAT, SOD, PX) and reduced inflammation in immune cells. Notably, oil obtained at the early flowering stage strongly lowered cytokine production (IL-6, IL-8, IL-1β, TNF-α). These results suggested that TEO, especially from the early flowering stage, could serve as a natural alternative therapy against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and related infections Pandur E et al. (2022) [64].

7. Formulations

Gupta, P et al. (2022) had formulated thyme oil nano emulsion against larvae of *A. stephensi*, *A. aegypti* and *C. tritaeniorhynchus*. And the study reported potent anti insecticide. Matteo Micucci et al (2020), *Thymus solid* essential oil possess antimicrobial, spasmolytic and antispastic. Kiani M et al (2017), had formulated toothpaste with *T. vulgaris* essential oil, which promising potent oral health.

8. Clinical evidences

Non pharmacologically *T. vulgaris* have been using for post viral acute cough [67]. Thyme oil showed potent antimicrobial and antioxidant activity [68]. Between 5 to 12 years old kids, with mild to moderate asthma exacerbation, the study showed significant change with *T. vulgaris* extract [69]. Nano liposome extract has shown potent positive and negative antibacterial activity [70].

CONCLUSION

In this review study, few *Thymus vulgaris* L. related data were included. *Thymus vulgaris* L. has numerous potent pharmacological activities in various solvents. *Thymus vulgaris* Linn. is a versatile medicinal herb enriched with bioactive compounds that contribute to its wide range of pharmacological activities. Its nutritional and therapeutic potential makes it valuable in

medicine, food, and cosmetics, though further research is needed to bridge existing gaps and fully explore its clinical applications.

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